

Ravshanov Khurshid Akramovich

Denov Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy Department of Finance and Banking teacher

Abstract. In the tax system of Uzbekistan, you will learn about the tax imposed on the property of legal entities and individuals, and that this tax is calculated as a fixed tax on resources in the form of basic funds, and also provide information about the amount of income from this tax to local budgets, and the stable income of the budget.

Key word. Funds, property tax, share of income, object of taxation, base, rate.

Introduction. The main purpose of the introduction of property tax in the tax system of our country is to arouse the interest of enterprises in selling their excess and unused property, on the other hand, it is to encourage the effective use of property on the balance sheet of enterprises. is also This, in turn, will make it possible for enterprises to renew their old physical and moral means with new, advanced technology-equipment, as well as reduce the price of manufactured goods, and create an opportunity to produce competitive goods.

Payers of property tax introduced in the tax system are considered legal entities and individuals and pay the taxes determined in accordance with the tax code. Now let's get acquainted with the information about how to collect property tax from legal entities and individuals and how to pay it.

One of the important steps towards the taxation of business activities in Uzbekistan was the introduction of the tax on the property of enterprises and the tax on the property of legal entities, which was adopted on February 15, 1991 and was introduced in 1992. Currently, the legal basis of this tax is the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Tax Service", the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other regulations related to tax legislation. - legal documents are also considered.

The tax imposed on the property of individuals was adopted on December 28, 1993 and was introduced by 1994 together with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Taxes on the Property of Individuals". The tax on the property of individuals is a regular tax that is collected once a year. The tax on the property of individuals is fiscally significant and forms part of the income of the state budget. Now let's have information about property tax payers and the object of taxation.

The tax payers of the tax imposed on the property of legal entities are:

- Legal entities of the Republic of Uzbekistan who own property that is considered an object of taxation in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the tax legislation;
- Legal entities that are non-residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, owning real estate in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Taxpayers of property tax levied on natural persons are natural persons, including foreign citizens, who own property recognized as the subject of taxation, agricultural holdings with or without legal entities.

The following are the objects of property taxation:

T/r	Object of taxation imposed on property of legal entities	Object of taxation imposed on property of individuals
1	Buildings and structures that must be registered in the state registration bodies of real estate rights	Non-residential real estate objects intended for business activities and income
2	Unfinished objects	Houses, apartments, country yard buildings
3	Railways, main pipelines, communication and power transmission lines, as well as facilities that are an integral technological part of these objects	Unfinished residential facilities
4	Residential real estate objects listed for later sale in the balance sheet of construction organizations or builders of buildings	Car accommodation, as well as other buildings, buildings and structures integrally connected to multi-apartment buildings

The tax rate for the property of legal entities is set at 1.5 percent. The tax rate for objects whose construction has not been completed within the regulatory period is set at 3 percent. Tax rates are set at 0.5 percent for:

1. Public railways, main pipelines, communication and power transmission lines, as well as facilities that are an integral technological part of these objects;
2. Immovable property and unfinished construction objects, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on conservation was adopted.

Amounts of property tax rates collected from individuals:

- 0.25 percent for houses and apartments, country yard buildings, car shelters integrally connected to multi-apartment buildings, as well as other buildings, buildings and structures;
- Houses and apartments located in cities, total area:
Over 200 sq.m and up to 500 sq.m - 0.33 percent
More than 500 square meters - 0.44 percent
- Houses and apartments with a total area of more than 200 square meters located in other population centers-0.33
- Taxable objects used for business activities or for leasing to a legal entity or an individual entrepreneur - 1.5 percent

The tax report is submitted to the tax authority at the place of tax registration once a year, during the period when the annual financial report is submitted. A calendar year is a tax period.

The changes in the tax system implemented in our country or the taxes collected are first of all non-refundable payments to the state budget, and all are taken into the state's financial account and base.

REFERENCES

1. SH. Torayev, R. Bozorov "Taxes and taxation" textbook
2. Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T.: "Adolat", 2008
3. Vahobov A.V., Jo`rayev A.S. Taxes and taxation: Textbook. - T.: Sharq, 2009. 448 p.
4. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Tax Service".//August 29, 1997
5. <http://www.lex.uz> -website of the base of laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan
6. <http://www.soliq.uz> - website of the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

